

CLIMATE CHANGES AND MEASURES TAKEN IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

If the meteorological events observed in the last 50-100 years are occurring more often, then it should be considered as the consequences of climate change occurring in the world. In addition to natural processes, there are also anthropogenic factors that cause emergency events. Scientific and technical progress, industrial development, human growth, annual increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere affect the climate. The overlap of these two factors causes global warming in the Earth's atmosphere. Therefore, anomalous and continuous heat is often observed in the summer months, and continuous cold in the winter months.

Keywords: climate change, global warming, natural disasters

In recent years, the growth of natural disasters in the world is more observed. Global climate changes, anomalous cold weather, earthquakes, tsunamis and floods, which result in the loss of a large number of people, are causing concern in Europe, as well as in Azerbaijan. Recent heavy precipitation (rain, hail, etc.), extreme heat in some places, acceleration of desertification processes are the most real examples of this [1].

Experts associate the causes of climate change with a number of factors. Since the surface of the Earth is not smooth, solar energy is distributed unevenly and causes the heating of both the oceans and the surface of the earth. The warming of the oceans also leads to the fact that the currents, currents and the formation of cyclones there take on a different character. It becomes stronger, the place of formation changes. On the surface of the earth, uneven distribution of energy leads to more heat in one place and cold in another, stronger rain and wind, or vice versa.

The more water evaporates from the Earth's surface into the atmosphere, the more it condenses and returns to the Earth in the form of rain. When raindrops condense, they incorporate pollutants in the atmosphere and eventually bring them to Earth. This pollution itself is unevenly distributed. This is also due to the increase in the number of people. As a person grows, his energy demand increases, the fuel burned increases, and the

pressure on the Earth's surface increases. The Earth's surface was heated before, that is, excess energy remained on the Earth at that time. Now there is desertification, deforestation, etc. makes it even tougher.

Climate change cannot be prevented. But certain measures can be taken:

- Observations conducted in Azerbaijan show that there is a temperature difference of 2°C between forested area and non-forested area [2, 3]. Therefore, by 2050, the area of forests in the country should be increased to 20-25% in order to lower the temperature by 2°C.

- In the future, the transition to alternative energy will be a very necessary process in this area. The construction of hydroelectric power stations on rivers would enable both energy production and flood prevention.

- As another measure, it is necessary to expand the use of drought-resistant plants in Azerbaijan.

The EUROSAT organization has published a joint final report on the audit of climate change, which was conducted with the participation of the Supreme Audit Institutions of 10 countries in Europe and shows that Azerbaijan pays serious attention to the issues of environmental and climate changes [4]. The purpose of the audit is as follows (table 1).

Table 1.

The purpose of the report on environmental and climate changes held in Azerbaijan with the participation of Supreme Audit Institutions (SAI).

№	The purpose of the report on environmental and climate changes in Azerbaijan
1	Monitoring climate change and its effects
2	Measures taken to reduce the effects of climate change
3	Forecasting the actual level of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere
4	Assessment of measures taken to address issues of accountability for climate change prevention measures

The result. Today, international organizations and individual states are looking for ways to escape from natural disasters caused by climate change. They carry out work on various topics in this field, using the possibilities of modern technologies, they investigate global climate changes, their consequences, and take preventive measures. Even in important international conferences, such topics are very prominent [6]. Speeches on various topics at those conferences draw

attention to such an issue that serious programs must be developed and implemented to save our rapidly changing world, and modern technologies are the main, leading ones in this field.

Literature

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